

Wound Detox

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Abstract— In the field of healthcare, automated wound diagnosis with advanced computer vision algorithms is becoming a potential area. This approach provides a quick and reliable way to diagnose various acute injuries such as abrasions, bruises, and cut wounds. In contrast to traditional manual assessment methods, which are not only time-consuming but also subjective, the advanced deep learning algorithms are used in automatic wound detection. In this paper, we study the automatic wound diagnosis across several clinical circumstances using CNN, an advanced real-time object detection system. Our study mainly aims by using CNN to detect and localize the acute injuries.

Keywords: Wound diagnosis, Computer Vision, CNN, Detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a “silent epidemic”, wounds not only cause severe physical pain to individual patients, such as background pain caused by the wound itself and operative pain from clinical interventions, but also introduce a certain degree of psychological impact, such as worry and anxiety in patients who suffer from traumatic pain, and in severe cases, it may lead to depression. However, the emergence of computer vision and deep learning techniques has inaugurated a new era in wound management, offering promising avenues for automating wound localization, identification, and classification. An accurate and thorough wound assessment is an essential component of optimal wound care. A wound assessment serves two important purposes: 1) to determine wound severity in order to predict expected rate of wound healing and develop a comprehensive plan of care and 2) to act as a reliable outcome measure that can be used to assess the effectiveness of a given wound treatment program. A key parameter that should be included in a wound assessment is the measurement of wound extent.

An innovative smartphone software called Wound Detox is transforming emergency wound care. It quickly recognizes and classifies injuries using cutting-edge image recognition technology, providing individualized treatment recommendations for cuts, abrasions, and other conditions. It gives people the confidence to address minor wounds by offering thorough treatment details and medications. It not only recommends therapies for moderate-level injuries but also identifies local hospitals that are qualified to handle particular ailments, guaranteeing prompt care. Users can optimize response times in emergency circumstances by simply clicking to summon ambulances using the integrated emergency response feature. Wound Detox revolutionizes the way we handle wound care during crises by seamlessly integrating technology, beneficial advice, and emergency services.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND OBJECTIVE

2.1 Problem Statement

The lack of immediate and accurate wound classification and first aid assistance can lead to improper treatment, especially in emergencies. To address this issue, we aim to develop a mobile application that allows users to quickly classify wounds and receive appropriate first aid information. The application will classify wounds into five categories: Abrasion, Bruise, Cut, Laceration, and Stab, with Abrasion and Bruise classified as low-level wounds, Cut and Laceration as medium-level wounds, and Stab as a high-level wound.

2.2 Objective

- Develop a user-friendly mobile application for wound classification and first aid assistance.
- Implement a machine learning model to classify wounds based on images uploaded by users.
- Provide appropriate first aid information for each classified wound type.
- Display nearby hospital information for medium and high-level wounds.
- Automatically provides a call option of an ambulance for high-level wounds.
- Ensure user data security and privacy.

III. METHODOLOGY

The system design for automated wound detection and assessment revolves around seamlessly integrating advanced machine learning algorithms tailored for clinical use. It begins with collecting and annotating diverse medical image datasets, followed by preprocessing to standardize image quality. Through careful evaluation and selection of machine learning algorithms, such as CNNs, and ensemble techniques, and training using transfer learning, the system ensures accurate wound detection and classification. Rigorous validation ensures reliability before deployment in clinical settings, empowering healthcare professionals to efficiently assess wounds and improve patient care outcomes.

In this wound detox application, we have gathered the wound dataset from Kaggle, it is an online platform that serves as a hub for data, offering a diverse range of datasets, competitions, and resources. Data enthusiasts can collaborate, compete, and learn through real-world data challenges, accessing valuable datasets, participating in competitions. Later we annotated these wound images using Roboflow. It is a platform offers tools for data annotation, pre-processing, and model training, simplifying the complexities of computer vision projects. By using these tools the wound images are classified into five classes namely- laceration, abrasions, bruises, cut and stab.

1. User Registration and Authentication: Users will be able to create accounts securely by providing necessary information such as username, email, and password. The system should verify user credentials by employing encryption techniques to protect sensitive data like passwords. Authentication mechanisms like two-factor authentication can be implemented to enhance security. Once authenticated, users will have access to the features and functionalities of the application.

2. Wound Image Upload and Analysis: Users can upload images of wounds from their mobile devices through the application interface. The system utilizes image recognition technology, possibly leveraging machine learning algorithms, to analyze the uploaded images. Image analysis identifies the type and severity of the wound, distinguishing between categories like cuts, burns, abrasions, etc. Advanced image processing techniques may be used to assess the depth, size, and condition of the wound accurately.

3. Personalized Treatment Recommendations: Based on the analysis of the wound image, the system generates personalized treatment recommendations. Recommendations can include wound care techniques such as cleaning methods, dressing types, and frequency of changing dressings. Medication suggestions may include over-the-counter or prescription medications for pain management, infection prevention, and wound healing acceleration. Recommendations are tailored to the specific type and severity of the wound detected, ensuring effective treatment.

4. Real-Time Medical Resource Locator: The system integrates with location-based services to identify nearby hospitals and medical facilities equipped to handle the identified type of injury. Users can view relevant information about these facilities, including ratings, distance from the user's location, available services (e.g., emergency room, trauma center), and contact information. Maps integration provides directions to the selected medical facility from the user's current location, facilitating prompt access to medical care.

5. Emergency Response Integration: In critical situations, users have the option to initiate an emergency response directly from the application. The system interfaces with emergency response services such as 911 or local emergency services to dispatch ambulances to the user's location. Users may be prompted to confirm the emergency before dispatching assistance to prevent false alarms. Location tracking technology ensures accurate identification of the user's whereabouts, expediting emergency response times.

Each of these functionalities contributes to the overall goal of providing users with comprehensive wound care support, from initial assessment and treatment recommendations to accessing appropriate medical facilities and emergency assistance when needed.

The below figure 3.1 shows the System Architecture and workflow of wound detox application.

Fig 3.1 System Architecture

IV. ALGORITHMS USED

Wound image prediction applications typically employ various algorithms depending on the specific task and requirements. Here are some common algorithms used in this domain:

1. **Machine Learning Algorithms:** Deep Learning (Convolutional Neural Networks - CNNs): CNNs are widely used for image analysis tasks, including wound image prediction. They can learn complex patterns and features from images, making them effective for tasks like wound segmentation, classification, and prediction. Convolutional Neural Networks are particularly powerful for wound image processing tasks due to their ability to automatically learn and extract hierarchical features from images. Here's how CNNs typically work in the context of wound image processing:

- Input Data - CNNs take images as input. In wound image processing, these images can be of varying resolutions and may contain color or grayscale information.
- Convolutional Layers: The first layers in a CNN are convolutional layers. Each layer consists of multiple filters or kernels that convolve across the input image. These filters learn various features such as edges, textures, and patterns relevant to wound analysis.
- Activation Functions: After convolution, an activation function like ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) is typically applied. ReLU helps introduce non-linearity, enabling the network to learn more complex relationships within the data.
- Pooling Layers: Pooling layers (e.g., max pooling or average pooling) follow convolutional layers. They reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps while retaining important information. Pooling helps in making the learned features more robust and invariant to small spatial variations.
- This vector is then fed into one or more fully connected layers, which learn high-level representations and relationships across the extracted features.
- Output Layer: The output layer of the CNN depends on the specific task. For wound image processing, it could be:

Overall, CNNs excel in wound image processing tasks by automatically learning relevant features from images, which can be crucial for tasks like wound detection, segmentation, classification and prediction.

2. **Image Processing Algorithms:** Edge Detection: Algorithms like Canny edge detection can help in outlining wound edges.
 - Morphological Operations: Techniques like dilation, erosion, and opening/closing can be used for refining segmented wound regions.
3. **Feature Extraction and Selection:**
 - Texture Analysis: Algorithms like Grey Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) can extract texture features useful for wound classification. Color Analysis: Analyzing color components in wound images can provide additional information for prediction. Shape Analysis: Algorithms that extract shape features like circularity, eccentricity, etc., can be useful in distinguishing different types of wounds.

4. Hybrid Approaches: Combining machine learning with image processing techniques for improved accuracy and efficiency.

- Using ensemble methods like combining multiple classifiers or algorithms to enhance prediction performance. The choice of algorithm depends on factors like the complexity of the task, the amount and quality of available data, computational resources, and the specific goals of the wound image prediction application.

V. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The wound detox mobile application where users register to create account. To continue with the registration process, users must provide required fields such username, password, and phone number. Following a successful registration. The user's account is validated and they can sign in with appropriate detail's.

Fig 5.1: User Registration

Fig 5.2: User Login

Fig 5.3: Upload picture (Minor Wound)

Users will be taken to the for the page displaying information when they have successfully signed in. After signing Users must capture the particular wound by clicking on “CAPTURE IMAGE” in order to upload. If the image uploads successfully, then click on “SUBMIT” and wait for few seconds to get the information on particular user images. In the above picture the user has captured wound and uploading it, in order to predictthe wound user have to click on “SUBMIT”. As soon as the user uploads image it classifies what kind of wound it is and helps the user by suggesting and prescribing.

Fig 5.4: First Aid prescription

Fig 5.5: Upload picture (Moderate Wound)

Fig 5.6: Hospital Address description

When user uploads an image successfully it classifies what kind of wound it is. If the wound is “MODERATE WOUND”. And it helps the user by prescribing and along with that it suggests a list hospitals near to the use, when the user have successfully uploads an image, it classifies what kind of wound, if the “WOUND IS MAJOR” and it helps the user by providing the near by hospitals as well as it calls a near by “AMBULANCE” for an medical emergency.

Fig 5.7: Upload picture
(Major Wound)

Fig 5.: Ambulance call

VI. CONCLUSION

We studied various current applications and recent advances in dee learning applied to wound images, introduced models in different tasks, reviewed publicly available datasets and summarize various data preprocessing approaches. Deep learning is still one of the active research areas in the field of wound image analysis. The reliable performance of deep learning in image classification, detection, and segmentation can effectively improve the diagnostic efficiency of health-care professionals. For areas with underdeveloped medical resources, it can compensate to a certain extent for the impact caused by the shortage of doctors. With the extensive cooperation of medical institutions, the rapid development of computer hardware and image acquisition equipment, and the continuous optimization of deep learning algorithms, deep learning has a very promising prospect in the field of wound image analysis.

VII. REFERENCES

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